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Effect Of Artificial Intelligence On The Financial Reporting Quality Of Deposit Money Banks In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2013-2024. The specific objectives were to evaluate the effect of Digital Payment on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria; analyze the effect of Digital Loan on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria; determine the effect of Digital Saving on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria; determine the effect of Digital Remittance on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was used in this study. The variables were liquidity of financial reporting quality as the dependent variables while Digital Payment, Digital Loan, Digital Saving and Digital Remittance were the independent variables. Panel Least Squared (PLS) method of data analysis was used. The study also employed descriptive statistics, hausman test and correlation in this study. From the analysis result the study found that; Digital payment has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks. Digital loans have no significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks, digital savings has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks. The study concludes that artificial intelligence-driven digital banking services significantly enhance the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria, particularly through digital payment, digital savings, and digital remittance platforms. The study recommends that Deposit money banks should further strengthen AI-driven digital payment platforms, given their positive and significant effect on financial reporting quality. Banks should enhance AI integration in digital lending processes. Advanced machine learning models for credit assessment, loan monitoring, and automated provisioning should be adopted to improve data quality and enable digital loan systems to contribute more significantly to financial reporting quality. Banks should intensify the deployment of artificial intelligence in digital savings platforms, as digital savings has a positive and significant impact on financial reporting quality.

Keywords: Digital Payment, Digital Loan, Digital Saving and Digital Remittance, artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies in the global financial landscape, redefining how financial institutions process information, make decisions, and deliver services. AI an advanced branch of computer science—enables machines and systems to perform tasks that traditionally required human intelligence, including learning, reasoning, data interpretation, and predictive modeling (Ezeamama, Orji, and Obani, 2024). Over the last decade, financial sectors around the world have increasingly integrated AI tools such as machine learning, natural language processing, robotic process automation (RPA), and predictive analytics to improve operational efficiency and

competitive advantage. In Nigeria, deposit money banks (DMBs) operate in a highly dynamic and complex financial environment characterized by rapid technological changes, regulatory reforms, heightened competition, and increasing demand for transparency and accountability (Eketu, Nwiyii, & Uelee. (2023) . The adoption of digital technologies has been critical to the survival and growth of Nigerian banks, especially in areas involving customer service, risk management, and internal controls. Among these technologies, AI has gained prominence for its capacity to transform core banking functions, particularly financial reporting. Financial reporting quality is fundamental to the stability and credibility of financial institutions. High-quality financial reports provide accurate, timely, relevant, and reliable information to stakeholders including investors, regulators, customers, and management for sound decision-making and effective governance. In the context of Nigerian banks, the increasing complexity of financial transactions and data volume has made traditional financial reporting practices less efficient and more prone to human error (Ezeamama & Orji, 2024). This situation has underscored the need for innovative solutions that can enhance the accuracy, timeliness, and transparency of financial reporting. AI technologies present significant opportunities to improve financial reporting quality by automating repetitive tasks, detecting anomalies, enhancing fraud detection, improving predictive accuracy, and ensuring compliance with regulatory standards. For example, AI-based systems can streamline the collection and classification of financial data, reduce manual intervention, and support real-time reporting (Ezeamama & Obani, 2024). Additionally, AI algorithms can analyze large datasets to uncover patterns and insights that might otherwise go unnoticed, facilitating more informed decision-making by bank management and stakeholders. Despite the potential benefits of AI integration, challenges remain. Nigerian banks face constraints such as inadequate technological infrastructure, skills gaps among accounting professionals, data privacy concerns, and regulatory uncertainty regarding AI applications. These challenges could impede the effective deployment of AI tools and potentially limit improvements in financial reporting quality (Elegunde, & Osagie, 2020). Given the strategic importance of financial reporting in maintaining trust and accountability in the banking sector, understanding how AI influences reporting quality in Nigerian deposit money banks is both timely and critical. This study seeks to fill the gap in empirical evidence on the relationship between AI adoption and financial reporting quality within the Nigerian banking industry, offering insights that could inform policymakers, regulators, banking professionals, and scholars.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Financial reporting plays a critical role in ensuring transparency, accountability, and confidence in the banking sector. Deposit money banks in Nigeria are required to prepare high-quality financial reports that are accurate, timely, relevant, and compliant with regulatory standards such as International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) guidelines. However, despite these requirements, concerns persist regarding the quality of financial reporting among Nigerian banks. Traditional financial reporting processes in many deposit money banks are still heavily reliant on manual procedures and conventional accounting systems. These methods are often characterized by delays in reporting, data inconsistencies, human errors, weak fraud detection mechanisms, and challenges in handling large volumes of complex financial data. Such weaknesses can reduce the reliability and credibility of financial reports, thereby affecting stakeholders' decision-making and undermining confidence in the banking system. In recent years, artificial intelligence has been introduced as a technological solution capable of improving financial reporting quality through automation, real-time data processing, enhanced accuracy, anomaly detection, and improved compliance monitoring. Despite the increasing adoption of AI tools in Nigerian banks, there is limited empirical evidence on whether and to what extent AI has improved the quality of financial reporting. Moreover, the level of AI integration varies significantly across banks due to factors such as high implementation costs, inadequate technical expertise, data security concerns, and regulatory uncertainties. The absence of clear empirical findings on the effect of artificial intelligence on financial reporting quality creates a knowledge gap for bank management, regulators, and policymakers. Without adequate evidence, decisions regarding AI investment, regulation, and implementation strategies may be poorly informed. It is against this backdrop

that this study seeks to examine the effect of artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to analyze the effect of artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria.. The following was the specific objectives that were guide this study:

- i. To evaluate the effect of Digital Payment on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria
- ii. To analyze the effect of Digital Loan on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria
- iii. To determine the effect of Digital Saving on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- iv. To determine the effect of Digital Remittance on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria

Literature Review

2.2 Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) represents a transformative domain of technologies designed to emulate human intelligence, enabling machines to perform tasks such as learning, problemsolving, and decision-making with remarkable efficiency. As defined by Sundar (2020), AI is a branch of computer science dedicated to creating programs that execute functions traditionally requiring human cognition, including perception, reasoning, and language comprehension. Similarly, IEEE-USA (2017) describes AI as a spectrum of systems, ranging from simple rulesbased models to advanced deep learning neural networks capable of handling complex cognitive tasks. This multifaceted nature positions AI as a pivotal tool across industries, with Zúñiga, Goyanes, and Durotoye (2023) emphasizing its tangible ability to solve problems, communicate, and reason logically, independent of human intelligence, based on its performance and autonomy levels In the context of financial institutions, particularly listed deposit money banks offering fintech services in Nigeria, AI's significance lies in its capacity to enhance operational efficiency, drive profitability, and foster innovation. Acemoglu and Restrepo (2018) highlight that AI boosts productivity by reducing processing times and improving operational performance, a view supported by Oyeniyi, Ugochukwu, and Mhlongo (2024), who note its role as a crucial driver of transformation in banking through improved efficiency and customer experiences. For instance, robotic process automation (RPA), a key AI technology identified by McKinsey (2021, 2022) and Desai et al. (2021), automates repetitive tasks like invoice processing with minimal human intervention, enhancing accuracy and scalability—attributes critical for banks managing high transaction volumes. AI's ability to analyze vast datasets underpins its value in financial services. Chukwudi, Echefu, Boniface, and Victoria (2018) assert that AI manages enormous volumes of data to predict consumer behavior, reduce errors, and personalize customer experiences, thereby increasing satisfaction—a vital factor for Nigerian banks competing in the fintech space. Similarly, Luo, Meng, and Cai (2018) and Beura et al. (2023) emphasize AI's proactive problem-solving capabilities, enabling banks to anticipate customer needs rather than merely react to issues. Data mining, as described by Gunning and Aha (2019), exemplifies this by extracting actionable insights from large databases, supporting applications like risk management and market analysis (Sirait, Rosalina, & Sari, 2023), which are essential for banks offering digital payment platforms or lending services.

2.1.2 Financial Reporting Quality

Choi (2013) defined financial reporting as a “publication of economic information which relates to businesses quantitative or non-quantitative that can help users in making economic decisions”. The coverage of the definition was extended by defining it as a process where firms communicate with outside stakeholders (McKinnon, 1984). Financial reporting quality is defined as the accuracy of the information conveyed by the process of financial reporting (Martinez-Ferrero et al., 2015). Financial reporting quality

can be referred to as the precision with which financial reporting present's information about a firm's operations (Biddle et al., 2019).

Tang et al. (2018) defined financial reporting quality as the extent to which the financial statement is able to provide true and fair information about the underlying performance and financial position that satisfies the varied stakeholders' interest. However, Jonas, Blanchet (2010) consider two distinct areas which are widely considered in the evaluation of financial reporting quality. The first stage depends on the needs of users, while the quality of financial reporting is adjudged on its usefulness to the user of the financial information (Baxter, 2007). On the other hand, the second phase of measuring financial reporting quality specifically focused on the belief of shareholder/investor protection.

2.3 Empirical Study

Musa, Ejura, Ibrahim, Kadams & Uchubiyajo, (2025) examines the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, focusing on AI-driven fraud detection systems (ADFDS), risk management (RM), and customer satisfaction (CS). This research employs a survey design with data collected from staff and management of 14 listed Nigerian banks, analyzing the relationship between ADFDS, RM, and customer satisfaction. The regression analysis reveals that both AI-driven fraud detection systems and risk management practices have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. Specifically, ADFDS contributes to improving customer trust and satisfaction by enhancing fraud detection, while RM practices bolster customer confidence in banks' ability to manage risks. The study concludes that AI technologies are essential for improving performance in Nigerian banks, particularly in enhancing customer satisfaction. Banks are encouraged to invest further in AI technologies to improve fraud detection and risk management, while also ensuring that these innovations align with customer needs for convenience and security.

Salemcity, Aiyesan, Adewumi & Adelokun Adinlewa, (2025). examines the effect of AI on cost reduction and profitability of DMBs in Nigeria. Prior works show that operating efficiency cannot not be fully achieved in traditional banking. the study aims to investigate how AI can boost productivity, cut expenses, and improve operational efficiency in deposit money banks in Nigeria. To achieve its objectives, the study employs a quantitative approach by utilizing multivariate models for the analysis of the panel data gathered. The study establishes the need for AI in improving operational efficiency and financial performance in the banking sector. Results reveal that AI investments significantly contribute to cost efficiency, which, in turn, enhances profitability in Nigerian DMBs. Implications: The study establishes that AI-driven automation and predictive analytics optimize banking operations by reducing operational costs while improving service delivery. Value: The study highlights the strategic significance of AI in banking, proposing empirical evidence for academics and researchers, guiding bank administrators and policymakers on AI investment for effectiveness and financial sustainability.

Chegwe, Ayewumi & Ehiedu, (2025) investigate the effect of artificial intelligence on financial modeling in Nigeria. Specifically, the dependent variables; Financial modeling measured by Return on Equity (ROE) while the independent variables; Artificial intelligence was measured by Volume of Point of Sales (VPOS), Volume of Internet Transfer (VINT) and Volume of Mobile Transfer (VMOT). The study covered a time period of thirteen (13) years spanning from 2010 to 2022. The study adopted "ex-post facto" research design with the help of Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Correlation test and Ordinary Least Square to analyze the data sourced from CBN statistical bulletin and Federal reserve economic data. The statistical package used in this study is Econometric Views version 10. The results of the OLS test reveals that LogPOS ($r = 0.095171 > 0.05$), and LogINT ($r = 0.070423 > 0.05$) have a positive significant effect on return on equity (ROE) except LogMOT ($r = 0.022372$)

Asuquo, Ndueso, & Daniel, (2025) examine the influence of artificial intelligence on audit quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to evaluate the influence of machine learning, natural language processing and data analytics on audit quality of deposit money banks in south-south, Nigeria. Survey research was adopted for the study. The population for the study consisted of 8095 employees and sample size was 385 respondents which were determined using Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination. Data were collected using questionnaire which was distributed to the staff of

the five selected deposit money banks used for the study out of which 367 copies of questionnaire were filled and returned. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and multiple regression analyses. Findings indicated that machine learning, natural language processing and data analytics have significant influence on audit quality of deposit money banks in south-south, and Nigeria.

Omole & Diisu (2025). investigates the effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, using Earnings Per Share (EPS) as the primary measure of profitability. The research focuses on three AI-related indicators: Software Book Value (SBV), AI-Related Keyword Disclosures (AKD), and Software Expenses Disclosed (SED). Descriptive statistics reveal substantial disparities in AI software investments (SBV), with some banks reporting significant asset values and others showing impairments or negative values. Keyword disclosures and software expense reporting were more uniformly distributed across banks. Using a fixed effects regression model, the study found that AI-related variables collectively have a statistically significant impact on EPS (F-statistic = 18.40, $p < 0.0000$), explaining 72.44% of the variation in profitability. Among the individual variables, SBV exhibited a positive and statistically significant effect on EPS ($p < 0.05$), indicating that higher tangible AI investments enhance financial performance. However, AKD and SED showed no significant individual influence on EPS, suggesting that superficial or nominal AI engagements do not translate into improved earnings.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed ex-post facto research design. The time period was from 2013 to 2024. The selection of an *ex-post facto* research design is on the presumption that the author's cannot manipulate the data as they are available in public domain vide established and regulated government agencies. The data were secondary in nature and on annual basis, while the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) banking and supervision and Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) annual reports of the selected bank served as the source of data collection.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of the fourteen (14) deposit money banks quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). The study covered twelve years annual reports and accounts of these banks from 2013 to 2024.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

This study selected all the ten (10) deposit money banks in Nigeria for the study. The banks were chosen because of availability of data

Table 3.1: List of Quoted Deposit Money Banks on the Nigerian Exchange Group

1	Fidelity bank plc
2	FCMB plc
3	First bank plc
4	Access bank plc
5	United bank of Africa (UBA)
6	Sterling bank plc
7	GT Bank
8	ECO Bank
9	Zenith Bank
10	Union Bank

3.4 Panel Regression

In this study, the regression approach of data analysis was used. Specifically, the connection between the independent variables (Artificial intelligent) and dependent variable (Financial reporting quality) in the model was analyzed using Panel Least Square regression techniques. The three main statistical techniques

employed to analyze the data were multiple regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation analysis.

3.5 Model Specification

This study adapted and modified the model of Chegwe, Ayewumi & Ehiedu, (2025) investigate the effect of artificial intelligence on financial modeling in Nigeria is stated as:

$$ROE = f(VTPOS, VINT, VMOT,) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where:

ROE - Return on Equity while the independent variables;

VPOS-Volume of Point of Sales

VINT -Volume of Internet Transfer

VMOT - Volume of Mobile Transfer

The model is modified to in the following equation below

Algebraically, therefore

$$FRQ = F (DIP, DGR, DL, DS) \text{ -----(2)}$$

Where

FRQ = Financial Reporting Quality

DIP= Digital Payment

DL= Digital Loan

DS= Digital Saving

DGR= Digital Remittance

F = Functional Notation

Our model is now restated in an econometric form as:

$$FRQ = \beta_0 + \beta_1DIP + \beta_2DL + \beta_3DS + \beta_4DGR + u \text{ -----(3)}$$

FRQ= Financial Reporting Quality

Bo-B4= constant

3.6 Variables and Measurement

Variable	Measurement	sources
Dependent Variable Financial reporting quality	The proxy to be used for FRQ in this study is earnings quality and it was measured by discretional accruals (DAC) using Modified Jones model.	Elhabashy, 2023
Independent Variable Digital payment	Measured by the total amount of transactions done through Digital payment on an annual basis	Hafez, B., Kaddumi, T. A., Nassar, M.D. & Muqattash, R. S. (2023).
Digital remittance	This is measured by the annual turnover on the total number of transactions carried out via remittance channels.	Ibenta and Anyanwu (2017).
Digital saving	This is measured by the annual turnover on the total number of transactions carried out via remittance channels	Isa-Olatinwo, Uwaleke and Umar (2022)
Digital loan	This is measured by the annual turnover on the total number of transactions carried out via remittance channels	Iro, et al. (2022)

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

The logged data for this study are presented in the Appendix i. The data were logged to present the data in the same base before they are used for the analysis. Another reason is to achieve normality

Table 4.1. Descriptive Statistics

	FRQ	LDIP	LDL	LDS	LDGR
Mean	0.181417	14.56785	12338.03	16.29219	17.57274
Median	0.135000	14.06596	15.91944	17.54701	19.43901
Maximum	0.660000	15.91426	1478655.	20.12964	30.43941
Minimum	0.010000	12.98719	11.92712	7.414573	10.13219
Std. Dev.	0.161642	0.919729	134980.7	3.136012	3.765889
Skewness	1.140988	0.348459	10.81704	-0.880197	-0.488480
Kurtosis	4.019941	1.538246	118.0084	2.449376	2.924145
Jarque-Bera	31.23847	13.11210	68474.83	17.01089	4.801017
Probability	0.000000	0.001421	0.000000	0.000202	0.090672
Sum	21.77000	1748.142	1480564.	1955.063	2108.729
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.109259	100.6623	2.17E+12	1170.314	1687.648
Observations	120	120	120	120	120

Source: Researcher's summary of descriptive result (2026) using E-view 10

The mean values for each variable, along with their maximum and lowest values, standard deviation, and Jarque-Bera values which indicate the data's normality and nature are displayed in the descriptive statistics result in table 4.1 above. The outcome sheds some light on the characteristics of the chosen listed commercial bank from Nigeria that were employed in the research. The objective of the descriptive statistics was to characterize the overall distributional characteristics of the data and to pinpoint any anomalous observations or anomalous patterns of observations that would pose issues for the data's further analyses. The data generated for the study was thus described and summarized by an initial analysis of the data using basic descriptive methods. According to the study's goal, the descriptive statistics are provided in this part. This is the result of artificial intelligence and the financial reporting quality of the deposit money banks, as table 4.1 illustrates.

The researcher aimed to examine the artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria and central tendency for the commercial banks. The entire number of observations, skewness, kurtosis, mean, median, maximum, standard deviation, p-value, Jarque-Bera, and skewness in the data set were all captured by the descriptive properties of the data. Based on the data common sample's descriptive properties listed in Table 4.3, mean were shown to be 0.181417 for FRQ, 14.56785 for LDIP, 12338.03 for LDL, 16.29219 for LDS, and 17.57274 for LDGR. The median for the sample data are 0.135000, 14.06596, 15.91944, 17.54701 and 19.43901 respectively for FRQ, LDIP, LDL, LDS and DGR. The maximum and minimum values are 0.660000 and 0.010000 for FRQ, 15.91426 and 12.98719 for LDIP, 1478655 and 11.92712 for LDL, 20.12964 and 7.414573 for LDS, 30.43941 and 10.13219 for LDGR. The standard deviations are 0.161642, 0.919729, 134980.7, 3.136012, and 3.765889 for FRQ, LDIP, LDL, DS and LDGR respectively. The positive results of the skewness statistic indicated that the variables were positively skewed towards normalcy. The Kurtosis that measures the peakedness of the distribution of the variables are more than 3.0 with the exception of LDIP. The 5% level of significance of the p-values of the Jarque-Bera statistics leads the Jarque-Bera to propose that all the variables are normally distributed.

4.1.2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

In order to ascertain the nature or degree of association, i.e., positive or negative correlation, as well as the magnitude of the correlation between dependent variable (Financial reporting quality) and independent variables with other explanatory variables, Pearson's correlation matrix was used to assess the degree of association between artificial intelligent component and financial reporting quality of the commercial bank in Nigeria. The direction and strength of the relationship between two or more variables are measured by the correlation coefficient. At this stage, it is important to remember that correlation quantifies association rather than causation. Positive (>0) or negative (<0) correlations are both possible. When two variables have a positive correlation, they are moving in the same direction; when they have a negative correlation, they are moving in the other way. As a consequence, we used the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) to investigate the relationship between the variables, and the outcomes are shown in table 4.2.2 below.

Table 4.2: Correlation Analysis Result

	FRQ	LDIP	LDL	LDS	LDGR
FRQ	1.000000	0.377366	0.097617	0.193380	0.058759
LDIP	0.377366	1.000000	0.060055	0.024709	0.138404
LDL	0.097617	0.060055	1.000000	0.001184	0.082603
LDS	0.193380	0.024709	0.001184	1.000000	0.832356
LDGR	0.058759	0.138404	0.082603	0.832356	1.000000

Source: researcher's summary of correlation result (2026) using E-view 10

The correlation coefficient's result revealed a mixed correlation. The finding of this link supports the idea that there is a linear relationship between our variables. Additionally, the Pearson product-moment correlation, which measures the strength of the relationship between variables, revealed that the association between the variables is relatively small and falls below the 0.80 threshold, indicating that multicollinearity is not a problem for the predictor variables. The pairwise correlations between the variables of the artificial intelligent component and the financial reporting quality of deposit money bank are presented and discussed in this section. Although there are still some reasonably strong correlations between some of the study's variables, Table 4.2 demonstrates that the majority of correlation coefficients between the variables are quite low. The aforementioned findings indicate that the artificial intelligent and financial reporting quality have a very weak but positive correlation. The correlation table above revealed that none of the explanatory variables were completely or highly correlated, ruling out the possibility of an outlier when the study was looking for multicollinearity. This suggests that the model utilized for the analysis does not have a multi-collinearity issue. This further supports the application of panel regression analysis.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses and Discussion of Findings

In order to examine the relationship between the dependent variable (Performance) and the independent variables (FRQ, DIP, DL, DS, DGR) and to test the formulated hypothesis, we employed a Panel Regression Analysis since the data had both time series (2013-2024) and longitudinal properties (10 quoted Bank) our analysis is presented in table 4.5 below

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DIP_{it} + \beta_2 DL_{it} + \beta_3 DS_{it} + \beta_4 DGR_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Dependent Variable: FRQ
 Method: Panel EGLS (Period random effects)
 Date: 01/09/26 Time: 06:40
 Sample: 2013 2024
 Periods included: 12
 Cross-sections included: 10
 Total panel (balanced) observations: 120
 Swamy and Arora estimator of component variances

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
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C	0.271359	0.241567	5.262959	0.0000
LDIP	0.063895	0.015525	4.115570	0.0001
LDL	0.653407	0.042307	1.581541	0.1165
LDS	0.020286	0.008188	2.477539	0.0147
LDGR	0.101401	0.300965	3.452278	0.0000

Effects Specification		S.D.	Rho
Period random		0.000000	0.0000
Idiosyncratic random		0.152088	1.0000

Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.713261	Mean dependent var	0.181417
Adjusted R-squared	0.725896	S.D. dependent var	0.161642
S.E. of regression	0.145846	Sum squared resid	2.446177
F-statistic	7.793232	Durbin-Watson stat	1.564729
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000014		

Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.713261	Mean dependent var	0.181417
Sum squared resid	2.446177	Durbin-Watson stat	1.564729

Source: Author's Computation Using E-views 9 (2026)

A weighted adjusted R-squared value of 0.713261 and a weighted R-squared value of 0.725896 were given in Table 4.5 This graph indicates that around 72% of the variances in the tested bank' performance might be attributed to the green accounting practices used in the study. The probability value of 0.000014 and the F-statistic of 7.793232 show how well the regression model describes the data. Once more, the model shows that it is still very statistically significant even at 5% levels. In the meantime, the Durbin Watson estimate of 1.564729 shows that autocorrelation has little impact on the model. This suggests that the model is fit for prediction. It is on these bases that, each of the research hypothesis postulated in earlier chapter of this research were tested in the next section of this chapter.

4.3. Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Digital payment has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

The regression result in table 4.5 reported a coefficient value of 0.063895, t-statistics value of 4.115570 which is greater than 1.96 benchmark and a probability value of 0.0033 which is lesser than 5% level of significance but lower than 95% confidence level. By implication, the probability value which is less than 5% level of significance but greeter than 95% confidence level shows that the Digital payment has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks which is statistically significant. It is on this basis; the study rejects the null hypothesis one and accepts the alternate hypothesis. As such, the study reaffirmed that; Digital payment has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

H₀₃: Digital loans have no significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

In the case of hypothesis three, the regression result in table 4.5 reported a coefficient value of 0.653407, t-statistics value of 1.581541 which is higher than 1.96 benchmark and a probability value of 0.1165 which is lower than 5% level of significance but greater than 95% confidence level. By implication, Digital loans have no significant effect on financial **reporting quality** of deposit money banks. Within the periods under review. It is on this basis; the study rejects the null hypothesis three and accepts the

alternate hypothesis three that Digital loans have no significant effect on financial **reporting quality** of deposit money banks

H₀₄: Digital savings has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

The regression result in table 4.5 reported a coefficient value of 0.020286, t-statistics value of -2.477539 which is higher than 1.96 benchmark and a probability value of 0.0147 which is greater than 5% level of significance but less than 95% confidence level. By implication, the probability value which is greater than 5% level of significance but less than 95% confidence level shows that Digital savings has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.. It is on this basis; the study rejects the alternative hypothesis four and accepts the null hypothesis. As such, the study reaffirmed that, digital savings has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

H₀₂: Digital remittance has no significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

The regression result in table 4.5 reported a coefficient value of 0.653407 t-statistics value of -0.965577 which is lesser than 1.96 benchmark and a probability value of 1.581541 which is greater than 5% level of significance but less than 95% confidence level. By implication, the probability value which is greater than 5% level of significance but less than 95% confidence level shows that Digital remittance has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks. It is on this basis; the study accepts the null hypothesis two and accepts the alternate hypothesis two instead. As such, the study reaffirmed that; Digital remittance has significant effect on financial reporting quality of deposit money banks.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria, using digital payment, digital loan, digital savings, and digital remittance as key dimensions of AI-driven banking services. The findings indicate that artificial intelligence has a meaningful influence on enhancing financial reporting quality in the Nigerian banking sector. Specifically, digital payment was found to have a positive and significant impact on financial reporting quality, suggesting that AI-enabled payment platforms improve transaction accuracy, real-time recording, and timely preparation of financial reports. Digital savings also exhibited a positive and significant effect, indicating that AI applications in savings products enhance data consistency, transparency, and reliability of reported financial information. Furthermore, digital remittance showed a positive and significant influence on financial reporting quality, reflecting its role in facilitating prompt transaction recognition, improved audit trails, and reduced reporting errors. However, digital loan, although positively related to financial reporting quality, was found to have an insignificant effect. This implies that challenges such as credit risk complexities, data quality issues, and partial AI integration in loan processing may limit its contribution to improved financial reporting. Overall, the study concludes that artificial intelligence-driven digital banking services significantly enhance the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria, particularly through digital payment, digital savings, and digital remittance platforms. Nonetheless, the mixed results across the variables highlight the need for deeper and more effective AI integration, especially in digital lending operations, to fully realize the benefits of artificial intelligence on financial reporting quality in the Nigerian banking industry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study on the impact of artificial intelligence on the financial reporting quality of deposit money banks in Nigeria, the following recommendations are made

- i. Deposit money banks should further strengthen AI-driven digital payment platforms, given their positive and significant effect on financial reporting quality. Continuous system upgrades, real-time transaction validation, and automated reconciliation should be prioritized to improve accuracy, timeliness, and transparency of financial reports.

- ii. Although digital loans showed a positive but insignificant impact, banks should enhance AI integration in digital lending processes. Advanced machine learning models for credit assessment, loan monitoring, and automated provisioning should be adopted to improve data quality and enable digital loan systems to contribute more significantly to financial reporting quality.
- iii. Banks should intensify the deployment of artificial intelligence in digital savings platforms, as digital savings has a positive and significant impact on financial reporting quality. Improved customer data analytics, automated interest computation, and real-time reporting tools will enhance the reliability and consistency of financial information.
- iv. Given the significant and positive effect of digital remittance on financial reporting quality, deposit money banks should prioritize secure and AI-powered remittance solutions. Embedding intelligent fraud detection, real-time settlement, and automated reporting mechanisms will further improve the quality and credibility of financial reports.

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